

ELSEVIER

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Cancer Treatment and Research Communications

journal homepage: www.sciencedirect.com/journal/cancer-treatment-and-research-communications

Editorial

The evolving landscape of systemic treatment for advanced hepatocellular carcinoma and biliary tract cancer

Primary liver malignancies such as hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) and biliary tract cancer (BTC) represent an important cause of cancer-related death worldwide [1,2]. Herein, we will briefly review current and future research avenues in this setting as an introduction to the more in-depth articles available in this special issue of *Cancer Treatment and Research Communications*.

HCC accounts for approximately the 80% of all primary liver tumors, and over the last decades the incidence of HCC has been steadily increasing, especially in Western countries [3]. Advanced disease is typically defined by macrovascular invasion or extrahepatic spread, and at this stage of disease, systemic treatment represents the gold standard – if performance status and liver function are preserved [4]. Tyrosine kinase inhibitors (TKIs) including sorafenib and lenvatinib in treatment-naïve patients, and regorafenib, cabozantinib, and ramucirumab in pretreated HCCs have played and still play a crucial role as systemic therapy of this malignancy [5–7]. Nonetheless, we have recently registered the advent of novel therapeutic strategies, including immune checkpoint inhibitors (ICIs) [8]. In fact, single-agent immunotherapy has been evaluated in patients with unresectable disease; however, the promising results observed in early phase clinical trials have not been confirmed by subsequent phase III studies on pembrolizumab and nivolumab monotherapy, despite these agents showed interesting response rates in advanced HCC patients [9,10].

In addition, combination therapies based on two immunotherapeutic agents or an ICI plus a TKI have been tested and are being investigated in HCC. In particular, 2020 has seen the publication of the highly anticipated results of the IMbrave150 phase III trial comparing the combination of the PD-L1 inhibitor atezolizumab plus the antiangiogenic agent bevacizumab versus sorafenib as first-line treatment [11]. Notably enough, after more than a decade from SHARP study, this landmark trial has established atezolizumab plus bevacizumab as novel standard of care for patients with unresectable disease [12,13]. In fact, the combination provided a survival benefit compared to sorafenib monotherapy, with this evidence that has been further corroborated by the updated results presented by Finn and colleagues, showing a median overall survival (OS) of 19.2 months and 13.4 months in treatment-naïve patients receiving atezolizumab-bevacizumab and sorafenib, respectively (Hazard Ratio [HR], 0.66; 95% CI, 0.52–0.85; $p = 0.0009$) [14]; in addition, median progression-free survival (PFS) by an independent review facility was 6.9 months and 4.3 months in the experimental and the control arm (HR, 0.65; 95% CI, 0.53–0.81; $p = 0.0001$) [14], and the updated analysis showed 8% of complete response rate for atezolizumab plus bevacizumab compared to 1% in the sorafenib arm. Notably enough, the results of IMbrave150 have represented a historical step

forward, and several other immune-based combinations are being assessed, having the potential to further modify the treatment landscape of unresectable HCC [15].

Of note, after years of controversial - if not indeed disappointing - results, the HCC medical community is witnessing a new era in the management of this liver tumor [16,17]. In this evolving landscape, what the future will be like? 2020 has shown historical shifts in the management of advanced HCC, with atezolizumab plus bevacizumab representing the novel mainstay of systemic treatment in front-line setting. However, several questions remain unanswered, including the identification of reliable biomarkers that could predict response to novel systemic treatments. Results of ongoing investigations hopefully will increase the number of medical treatment options and the prognosis and quality of life of these patients, having the potential to further shape the outlook of the front-line and later-line setting in advanced HCC.

BTCs encompass gallbladder cancer (GBC), ampulla of Vater cancer (AVC), intrahepatic cholangiocarcinoma (iCCA), and extrahepatic cholangiocarcinoma (eCCA), with the latter further subclassified into perihilar (pCCA) and distal cholangiocarcinoma (dCCA) [18]. Although surgical resection remains the major established curative therapy for early-stage disease, resectability remains low at approximately 15–20% since most of patients are diagnosed with advanced disease [19]. Adjuvant treatment with capecitabine monotherapy has been recently suggested to improve OS in BTC patients, based on the results of the BILCAP trial [20,21]; however, this randomized, multicenter phase III study failed to meet its primary endpoint in terms of intention-to-treat analysis, with a median OS of 51.1 months in patients receiving a 6-month course of oral capecitabine compared to 36.4 months in the observation alone group (HR, 0.81; 95% CI, 0.63–1.04; $p = 0.0097$) [22]. At the same time, according to the pre-specified sensitivity analysis adjusted for gender, tumor grade, and nodal status, a statistically significant benefit in the capecitabine arm was observed, with HR for OS of 0.71 (95% CI, 0.55–0.92; $p = 0.01$).

In patients with metastatic disease, more than ten years after the publication of the ABC-02 phase III trial, the combination of cisplatin plus gemcitabine (CisGem) remain the reference doublet in treatment-naïve patients [23]. In this study, median OS of 11.7 months and 8.1 months were observed in patients receiving CisGem and gemcitabine monotherapy, respectively (HR, 0.64; 95% CI, 0.52–0.80; $p < 0.001$) [24]. However, most of patients experienced a short-term benefit from CisGem and other systemic treatment, with the majority of BTCs reporting a median survival inferior of a year; thus, huge efforts have been conducted over the last decade with the aim of identifying more effective treatment options [25,26]. In particular, the BTC medical

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ctarc.2021.100360>

Available online 23 March 2021

2468-2942/© 2021 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

community has registered the advent of molecular profiling through next-generation sequencing, that has led to the identification of novel targetable alterations - including fibroblast growth factor receptor (FGFR) aberrations, isocitrate dehydrogenase-1 (IDH-1) mutations, BRAF mutations, and neurotrophic tyrosine kinase (NTRK) gene fusions [27-30]. In fact, according to recent studies, approximately 40% of BTCs harbor actionable mutations, with the frequency of molecularly actionable alterations appearing higher in ICCA patients [31,32]. FGFR targeted therapies have entered in the clinical practice of cholangiocarcinoma, based on the results of clinical trials evaluating FGFR inhibitors in patients harboring specific aberrations. In particular, on April 2020, the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) granted accelerated approval of the FGFR1, FGFR2, and FGFR3 inhibitor pemigatinib, on the basis of the phase II FIGHT-202 study - as we shall see in further detail in this special issue [33,34]. In addition, several other FGFR inhibitors are currently under assessment, and important efforts have been made aiming at identifying predictors of response to FGFR inhibitors and resistance mechanisms [35].

Similarly, IDH inhibitors are being tested in this setting, as witnessed by the recently published ClarIDHy phase III trial evaluating the role of ivosidenib in IDH-1 mutant cholangiocarcinoma patients [36]; in addition, novel combinations including dabrafenib and trametinib have reported interesting results in the ROAR phase II trial on patients with BRAF^{V600E}-mutated cholangiocarcinoma [37]. Lastly, immunotherapy is trying to find its niche in BTC therapeutic landscape, despite its efficacy as monotherapy seems limited so far, according to recently presented and published trials [38-41].

Based on these premises, the treatment of primary liver cancers has changed significantly over the past several years, with the development of multiple novel systemic therapies for advanced-stage disease and novel therapeutic approaches for earlier stage disease [42-44]. These and other advances in the treatment of HCC and BTC are discussed in further detail in this special issue of *Cancer Treatment and Research Communications*.

Author contribution

All authors contributed equally.

Funding

The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Financial and Competing Interests Disclosure

The authors have no relevant affiliations or financial involvement with any organization or entity with a financial interest in or financial conflict with the subject matter or materials discussed in the manuscript. This includes employment, consultancies, honoraria, stock ownership or options, expert testimony, grants or patents received or pending, or royalties.

No writing assistance was utilized in the production of this manuscript.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The author has no relevant affiliations or financial involvement with any organization or entity with a financial interest in or financial conflict with the subject matter or materials discussed in the manuscript. This includes employment, consultancies, honoraria, stock ownership or options, expert testimony, grants or patents received or pending, or royalties.

References

- [1] A. Noonan, T.M. Pawlik, Hepatocellular carcinoma: an update on investigational drugs in phase I and II clinical trials, *Expert Opin Investig Drugs* 28 (11) (2019) 941–949.
- [2] J.M. Banales, J.J.G. Marin, A. Lamarca, et al., Cholangiocarcinoma 2020: the next horizon in mechanisms and management, *Nat Rev Gastroenterol Hepatol* 17 (9) (2020) 557–588.
- [3] S. De Lorenzo, F. Tovoli, M.A. Barbera, et al., Metronomic capecitabine vs. best supportive care in Child-Pugh B hepatocellular carcinoma: a proof of concept, *Sci Rep* 8 (1) (2018 Jul 3) 9997.
- [4] O. Waidmann, J. Trojan, Novel drugs in clinical development for hepatocellular carcinoma, *Expert Opin Investig Drugs* 24 (8) (2015) 1075–1082.
- [5] S. Faivre, L. Rimassa, R.S. Finn, Molecular therapies for HCC: looking outside the box, *J Hepatol* 72 (2) (2020) 342–352.
- [6] J.M. Llovet, R. Montal, D. Sia, R.S. Finn, Molecular therapies and precision medicine for hepatocellular carcinoma, *Nat Rev Clin Oncol* 15 (10) (2018) 599–616.
- [7] A. Rizzo, M. Nannini, M. Novelli, et al., Dose reduction and discontinuation of standard-dose regorafenib associated with adverse drug events in cancer patients: a systematic review and meta-analysis, *Ther Adv Med Oncol* 12 (2020), 1758835920936932.
- [8] L. Rimassa, T. Pressiani, P. Merle, Systemic Treatment Options in Hepatocellular Carcinoma, *Liver Cancer* 8 (6) (2019) 427–446.
- [9] M. Pinter, R.K. Jain, D.G. Duda, The Current Landscape of Immune Checkpoint Blockade in Hepatocellular Carcinoma: a Review, *JAMA Oncol* 7 (1) (2021) 113–123.
- [10] T. Yau, J. Park, R. Finn, et al., CheckMate 459, A randomized, multi-center phase III study of nivolumab (NIVO) vs sorafenib (SOR) as first-line (1L) treatment in patients (pts) with advanced hepatocellular carcinoma (aHCC), *Ann Oncol* 30 (2019) v874–v875.
- [11] R.S. Finn, S. Qin, M. Ikeda, et al., IMbrave150 Investigators. Atezolizumab plus Bevacizumab in unresectable hepatocellular carcinoma, *N Engl J Med* 382 (20) (2020) 1894–1905.
- [12] R.K. Kelley, Atezolizumab plus Bevacizumab - A landmark in liver cancer, *N Engl J Med* 382 (20) (2020) 1953–1955.
- [13] D.J. Pinato, N. Guerra, P. Fessas, et al., Immune-based therapies for hepatocellular carcinoma, *Oncogene* 39 (18) (2020) 3620–3637.
- [14] R.S. Finn, S. Qin, M. Ikeda, et al., IMbrave150: updated overall survival (OS) data from a global, randomized, open-label phase III study of atezolizumab (atezo) + bevacizumab (bev) versus sorafenib (sor) in patients (pts) with unresectable hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC), *J Clin Oncol* 39 (3, suppl) (2021), 267–267.
- [15] A. Rizzo, A.D. Ricci, G. Brandi, Immune-based combinations for advanced hepatocellular carcinoma: shaping the direction of first-line therapy, *Future Oncol* (2021). Jan 29.
- [16] M. Kudo, Scientific rationale for combined immunotherapy with PD-1/PD-L1 antibodies and VEGF inhibitors in advanced hepatocellular carcinoma, *Cancers (Basel)* 12 (5) (2020) 1089.
- [17] M. Bouattour, N. Mehta, A.R. He, E.I. Cohen, J.C. Nault, Systemic treatment for advanced hepatocellular carcinoma, *Liver Cancer* 8 (5) (2019) 341–358.
- [18] R.K. Kelley, J. Bridgewater, G.J. Gores, A.X. Zhu, Systemic therapies for intrahepatic cholangiocarcinoma, *J Hepatol* 72 (2) (2020) 353–363.
- [19] A. Lamarca, J. Barriuso, M.G. McNamara, J.W. Valle, Molecular targeted therapies: ready for “prime time” in biliary tract cancer, *J Hepatol* 73 (1) (2020) 170–185.
- [20] A. Rizzo, G. Brandi, Pitfalls, challenges, and updates in adjuvant systemic treatment for resected biliary tract cancer, *Expert Rev Gastroenterol Hepatol* (2021 Feb 11), <https://doi.org/10.1080/17474124.2021.1890031>.
- [21] A. Rizzo, G. Brandi, BILCAP trial and adjuvant capecitabine in resectable biliary tract cancer: reflections on a standard of care, *Expert Rev Gastroenterol Hepatol* 18 (2020 Dec) 1–3.
- [22] A. Rizzo, G. Brandi, Adjuvant systemic treatment in resected biliary tract cancer: state of the art, controversies, and future directions, *Cancer Treat Res Commun* 27 (2021 Feb 12), 100334, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ctarc.2021.100334>. Epub ahead of print PMID: 33592563.
- [23] J. Valle, H. Wasan, D.H. Palmer, et al., ABC-02 Trial Investigators. Cisplatin plus gemcitabine versus gemcitabine for biliary tract cancer, *N Engl J Med* 362 (2010) 1273–1281.
- [24] R.T. Shroff, M.M. Javle, L. Xiao, et al., Gemcitabine, cisplatin, and nab-paclitaxel for the treatment of advanced biliary tract cancers: a phase 2 clinical trial, *JAMA Oncol* 5 (6) (2019 Jun 1) 824–830.
- [25] Q.U.A.R. Sipra, R. Shroff, The impact of molecular profiling on cholangiocarcinoma clinical trials and experimental drugs, *Expert Opin Investig Drugs* (2020 Nov 23) 1–4.
- [26] G. Botrus, P. Raman, T. Oliver, T. Bekaii-Saab, Infigratinib (BGJ398): an investigational agent for the treatment of FGFR-altered intrahepatic cholangiocarcinoma, *Expert Opin Investig Drugs* (2021 Jan 4) 1–8.
- [27] A. Massa, C. Varamo, F. Vita, et al., Evolution of the experimental models of cholangiocarcinoma, *Cancers (Basel)* 12 (8) (2020) 2308.
- [28] L. Baiocchi, K. Sato, B. Eksler, et al., Cholangiocarcinoma: bridging the translational gap from preclinical to clinical development and implications for future therapy, *Expert Opin Investig Drugs* (2020 Dec 8) 1–11.
- [29] A. Rizzo, A.D. Ricci, S. Tavoroli, G. Brandi, Circulating tumor DNA in biliary tract cancer: current evidence and future perspectives, *Cancer Genomics Proteomics* 17 (5) (2020) 441–452.
- [30] S. Rizvi, S.A. Khan, C.L. Hallemeier, R.K. Kelley, et al., Cholangiocarcinoma - evolving concepts and therapeutic strategies, *Nat Rev Clin Oncol* 15 (2) (2018) 95–111.

- [31] S. Chakrabarti, M. Kamgar, A. Mahipal, Targeted therapies in advanced biliary tract cancer: an evolving paradigm, *Cancers (Basel)* 12 (8) (2020 Jul 24) 2039.
- [32] J.W. Valle, A. Lamarca, L. Goyal, et al., New horizons for precision medicine in biliary tract cancers, *Cancer Discov* (2017) 10–8290.
- [33] G.K. Abou-Alfa, V. Sahai, A. Hollebecque, et al., Pemigatinib for previously treated, locally advanced or metastatic cholangiocarcinoma: a multicentre, open-label, phase 2 study, *Lancet Oncol* (2020), [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045\(20\)30109-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045(20)30109-1). Published online.
- [34] A. Rizzo, A.D. Ricci, G. Brandi, Pemigatinib: hot topics behind the first approval of a targeted therapy in cholangiocarcinoma, *Cancer Treat Res Commun* 27 (2021 Feb 18), 100337, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ctarc.2021.100337>. Epub ahead of print PMID: 33611090.
- [35] A. Rizzo, A.D. Ricci, G. Brandi, Futibatinib, an investigational agent for the treatment of intrahepatic cholangiocarcinoma: evidence to date and future perspectives, *Expert Opin Investig Drugs* (2020 Oct 25) 1–8, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13543784.2021.1837774>. Epub ahead of print PMID: 33054456.
- [36] A. Angelakas, A. Lamarca, R.A. Hubner, M.G. McNamara, J.W. Valle, Ivosidenib: an investigational drug for the treatment of biliary tract cancers, *Expert Opin Investig Drugs* (2021 Mar 8), <https://doi.org/10.1080/13543784.2021.1900115>. Epub ahead of print PMID: 33683991.
- [37] V. Subbiah, U. Lassen, E. Élez, et al., Dabrafenib plus trametinib in patients with BRAF^{V600E}-mutated biliary tract cancer (ROAR): a phase 2, open-label, single-arm, multicentre basket trial, *Lancet Oncol* 21 (9) (2020 Sep) 1234–1243, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045\(20\)30321-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045(20)30321-1). Epub 2020 Aug 17 PMID: 32818466.
- [38] A. Rizzo, A.D. Ricci, G. Brandi, PD-L1, TMB, MSI, and other predictors of response to immune checkpoint inhibitors in biliary tract cancer, *Cancers (Basel)* 13 (3) (2021) 558, 2021 Feb 1.
- [39] A. Vogel, M. Bathon, A. Saborowski, Immunotherapies in clinical development for biliary tract cancer, *Expert Opin Investig Drugs* 31 (2020 Dec) 1–13, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13543784.2021.1868437>. Epub ahead of print PMID: 33382361.
- [40] A. Rizzo, A.D. Ricci, G. Brandi, Recent advances of immunotherapy for biliary tract cancer, *Expert Rev Gastroenterol Hepatol* (2021 Jan 8) 1–10, <https://doi.org/10.1080/17474124.2021.1853527>. Epub ahead of print PMID: 33215952.
- [41] A.D. Ricci, A. Rizzo, G. Brandi, Immunotherapy in biliary tract cancer: worthy of a second look, *Cancer Control* 27 (3) (2020 Jul-Aug), <https://doi.org/10.1177/1073274820948047>, 1073274820948047 PMID: 32806956; PMCID: PMC7791443.
- [42] J. Wang, S. Ilyas, Targeting the tumor microenvironment in cholangiocarcinoma: implications for therapy, *Expert Opin Investig Drugs* (2020 Dec 28) 1–10, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13543784.2021.1865308>. Epub ahead of print PMID: 33322977.
- [43] A. Rizzo, A.D. Ricci, G. Brandi, Durvalumab: an investigational anti-PD-L1 antibody for the treatment of biliary tract cancer, *Expert Opin Investig Drugs* (2021 Mar 9) 1–8, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13543784.2021.1897102>. Epub ahead of print PMID: 33645367.
- [44] S. Nakano, Y. Eso, H. Okada, A. Takai, K. Takahashi, H. Seno, Recent advances in immunotherapy for hepatocellular carcinoma, *Cancers (Basel)* 12 (4) (2020 Mar 25) 775, <https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers12040775>. PMID: 32218257; PMCID: PMC7226090.

Alessandro Rizzo*

Department of Experimental, Diagnostic and Specialty Medicine, S. Orsola-Malpighi University Hospital, Bologna, Italy

* Alessandro Rizzo, Department of Experimental, Diagnostic and Specialty Medicine, S. Orsola-Malpighi University Hospital, Bologna, Italy.

E-mail address: rizzo.alessandro179@gmail.com.